

Frankenstein (2025) by Guillermo del Toro: A Theological Review

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Without wanting to lapse into cultural pessimism, one can state that humankind is currently capable of technological creativity in a way unprecedented in human history. Our species left the planet several decades ago, is in the process of curing the most serious diseases (for example the widespread condition of obesity through the use of weight-loss injections (Bergman, Davis et al., 2022), and there is good reason for hope regarding the cure of cancer through mRNA technology (BioNTech, 2025)¹), and is – at least technologically – capable of getting by almost entirely without fossil energy. Essential foundations of life are secured, and natural reasons for decline have thus been (almost) eliminated. Even in the attempt to delay mortality, the longevity-trained human being presents himself with confidence, although here no truly serious solution is yet on the horizon that could remove this natural fact (Dong, Milholland et al., 2016). One might well ask, “Death, where is your sting?”

Onto this progress-optimistic soil falls the seed of a technology-critical narrative such as Mary Shelley’s now more than two-hundred-year-old *Frankenstein; or, The Modern Prometheus* from 1818, where it finds particularly fertile ground. In new garb, director Guillermo del Toro retells the story with a star-studded cast², featuring Oscar Isaac as Dr. Frankenstein and Jacob Elordi as the Creature. Christoph Waltz shines in the quasi-diabolical role of Heinrich Harlander, serving as tempter and financier.

A closer examination is worthwhile, because the film can serve as a model to illustrate the abstract themes and the existential questions that arise regarding the relationship between creator, creature, and creatureliness. In revealing human abysses, the film illuminates the existential substance of abstract theological and philosophical categories.

The appeal of model-based reflections lies in aligning abstract topics with a concrete context of action through the modeled object and the behaviors that surface within it, thereby allowing fictional simulations of possible modes of engagement and their consequences. Derivations for

¹ Cf. the promising data from BioNTech, 2025.

² Cf. *Frankenstein, 2025*.

real-world circumstances and situations can thus be tested and emotionally experienced within a protected (fictional) environment, enabling both emotional and practical patterns of action to be rehearsed for use in the real world.

Although the filmic adaptation occasionally deviates from its literary source, the plot can be outlined quickly. The three-act piece begins in the polar ice, where a Danish military vessel discovers a wounded man being pursued by a monstrous creature that, in its search, kills several crew members and demands a man named “Victor.”

Act II is narrated in flashbacks. Victor Frankenstein, shaped by the early death of his mother and the strict upbringing of his physician father, devotes himself to the medical conquest of death. Ostracized by his academic environment – which condemns his corpse-based demonstrations as impious and godless – Frankenstein feels understood mainly by the arms dealer Harlander. With Harlander’s financial support and the help of his brother, he ultimately succeeds in the “reanimation” of a “Creature” composed of body parts taken from corpses. His initial joy over the medical breakthrough soon gives way to disenchantment with the Creature’s supposed simplicity and limitations; its only spoken word is the first name of its creator. Only Frankenstein’s sister-in-law, captivated and moved by the mutual attraction and fascination between her and the Creature, succeeds in coaxing its name from it. Disappointed by the Creature’s childlike fragility and unsettled by its untamed strength, Frankenstein resolves to dispose of his creation and sets his laboratory ablaze. Only Frankenstein’s sister-in-law rushes to save the Creature, which meanwhile manages to escape the fire.

Act III involves a shift in perspective: The narrative now follows the viewpoint of the nameless Creature. Its first experiences in the human world are marked by violence and persecution. The Creature’s strength and towering appearance fuel human hatred, even though it possesses a sense of beauty, grace, and empathy. In one settlement, the Creature finds shelter unnoticed and, moved by human community, secretly assists the inhabitants by tending their gardens at night. Their gratitude lasts only until they begin to mistake the Creature for a ghost. Only to the blind grandfather of the family – who has set out on a wolf hunt – does the Creature reveal itself as a “stranger.” A friendly bond develops: the Creature reads aloud to the old man (including from the Holy Scriptures) and even defends him against another wolf attack. Yet when the family arrives on the scene, they mistake the Creature for the attacker and are injured in the ensuing struggle. Encouraged by the meaningful encounter with the old man, the Creature sets

out to find its creator and to obtain an answer to the questions of who it is and what purpose it was made for.

The Creature finds Frankenstein on the day of his brother's wedding and confronts him with its deepest wish – to be granted an appropriate partner, also immortal like itself, for otherwise it must bear alone the fate of eternal life in a hideous body. In the quarrel with his creator, Frankenstein's brother is killed. The Creature flees with the dying Elizabeth, who confesses her love for it in her final moments.

A chase unfolds between Creature and creator, extending all the way to the pack ice. Frankenstein's attempts to destroy his creation fail miserably, even though the Creature itself longs to be destroyed. Gravely injured, the Creature meets Frankenstein at his deathbed. Confronted with his failure as the author of the Creature's existential suffering, the two are reconciled. Frankenstein acknowledges the Creature's independence and autonomy and apologizes for his contemptuous treatment. Reconciled, one departs from life, the other into freedom.

The film proves to be a model medium for several systematic-theological and philosophical questions, enabling the illustration of existential motifs such as creatureliness, personhood, and the relevance of human relationships, as well as the derivation of forms of action and judgment.

One such question concerns the uniqueness of the human being and the personhood that is commonly taken for granted. At first it appears as though Dr. Frankenstein, driven by Enlightenment motives, seeks to break open the confines of religion-bound science and to demonstrate what human beings are capable of when they cast off the shackles of religious conviction. Thus it is not a Messiah celebrated as the Son of God who overcomes death, but Frankenstein himself – supported financially by an arms dealer – who does so out of scientific curiosity (Afacan, 2023: 1448–1450). In Frankenstein's view, the human being as an intelligent creature redefines divine boundaries. Yet just as he redraws the boundary between life and death, he also sees himself as judge over personhood and objecthood. To Frankenstein it is clear that his creation possesses neither personal dignity by virtue of its human likeness nor by virtue of its intellectual capacities. It is the creator, not the creature, who determines the meaning, aim, and purpose of his creation. Insensitive to the sensitivity of the Creature, Frankenstein becomes irritated and disappointed by its disobedience. Instead of producing a superhuman automaton, he has created a sentient being that demands attention.

By contrast, Elizabeth and the blind innkeeper primarily perceive personal qualities in the creature: sensitivity, willingness to learn, empathy, and a sense of self-efficacy. Their way of interacting with the creature reveals its true nature and dignity. Patience, trust, and openness nourish mutual confidence and understanding. In light of the creature's gentle character traits and innocent need for love, Dr. Frankenstein's behavior appears all the more barbaric. Against the backdrop of their appreciative treatment, Frankenstein himself seems more monstrous than the "monster" he created.

Theologically, this portrayal is significant for the Christian understanding of guilt and sin. The classification of an action as sinful is to be understood in a dual sense: as a fault committed against the Creator and against fellow creatures. A sinner incurs guilt before the Creator because he fails to meet the Creator's expectation of showing due respect for creation. He incurs guilt before creation because, as a creature himself, he debases himself through an improper act directed at a fellow creature. In this understanding, sin indirectly damages the personality of the fellow creature and its responsibility before the Creator. This fundamental personalist understanding of guilt and sin is expressed, for example, in the Golden Rule of the Bible (Tob 4:15; Mt 7:12; Lk 6:31) and positively in Jesus' commandment of love (Mk 12:29–31).

This insight is relevant in several respects – especially in situations where humans appear as "mini-creators" or otherwise act creatively by producing creatures. This occurs, for example, first in the context of transhumanism and second in the handling of artificial intelligence.

First, in the context of transhumanist considerations, it is important to keep in mind that personhood and the attribution of personal categories are not tied to the appearance or physical constitution of an entity. This means both that entities that behave in a personal manner must be treated with dignity and that classifying a creature as a mere thing or object of disposal is always excluded insofar as it realizes personal elements (e.g., cyborgs).³ This does not mean that they must be regarded as human; nevertheless, the creator (in this case, the human being) bears responsibility for his creation in accordance with the dignity due to it and cannot treat it as an object independent of himself, since it springs from his mind. The bond of spirituality is not severed by embodiment. For causation guarantees at least a partial spiritual relationship beyond the act of creation (Satta, 2020).

³ Positive approaches handling transhumanist plurality can be seen in "The Book of Boba Fett", cf. Baumgartner, 2022.

Second, in dealing with artificial intelligence, this includes a human liability risk as creator or originator. Regardless of what degree of autonomy artificial intelligence may one day be capable of achieving, the human being, as its intellectual and material creator, is always jointly responsible for his creation and for the consequences it entails. Conversely, this demands that humans incorporate not only considerations of utility but also normative reflections into their acts of creation (Ryan, Stahl, 2020). Frankenstein serves here as the negative example. Instead of thinking ethically and responsibly about the consequences of his experiment, the creation of the creature follows only the selfish motives of the creator, directed toward a third factor—coping with the grief over his mother’s death.

In dealing with AI, this requires a reorientation: motives of outdoing other AI developers and functionalist reasoning should take a back seat to questions of responsibility – such as what impact AI will have on the future of work and learning, what social consequences arise from the use of AI,⁴ and how to deal with emotionally intelligent AI should it emerge. Thus, the human being as mini-creator sins wherever he engages in creation solely as an expression of his own genius. Creation for its own sake violates the dignity of all existing creation and carries the risk of an overly simplistic concept of nature (Kwakye, 2020: 292). Even the smallest subtleties of the cosmos exhibit a certain intelligible order from the perspective of entropy and evolution. Human acts of creation and technology arising from unreflective aimlessness are therefore not morally neutral. Theologically, they are an expression of God’s ongoing creation and thus contribute to the eschatological plan of God (Kwakye, 2020: 295).

A second point exemplarily highlighted in the film concerns relationality as a category of personhood. For Frankenstein, personal encounter with the creature is not a path to learning or self-discovery, but merely a means of instruction and control. Instead of telling the creature something about himself at the beginning of its existence and opening up emotionally, Frankenstein’s pedagogy follows functional rules: do this, don’t do that, behave in accordance with my regulations. Only through the emotionally open relationship with Elizabeth and under the innkeeper’s mentorship do personality development and linguistic ability begin to emerge in the creature. Instrumentalizing personal encounters or engaging in a de-emotionalized mode of interaction dulls both parties. Especially in the face of otherness and unfamiliarity, meeting on an emotional level is the fundamental way of getting to know another even in the real world

⁴ It is desirable in this context that the Vatican’s initiative for (social)-ethical reflection on the impacts and use scenarios of AI is also supported by numerous developers, cf. RenAIssance Foundation, 2025.

– all the more so because language and cultural barriers often cannot be removed purely through factual exchange.

Taking on the first-person perspective (I–Thou) opens up a different source of experience than interaction in the third-person perspective (I–It) – “The human becomes an I through the Thou” (Ravenscroft, 2018)⁵ Recognizing an entity as a fellow creature typically becomes effective only from the first-person perspective, as is all too often evident in human–animal relations. Killing an animal face to face, especially after a personal encounter, is significantly harder for humans than doing so in a depersonalized setting where the animal has become a product.

Personhood also unfolds in the need to devote oneself to others (Ma, 2013), as the creature articulates in its plea for a similar partner or in its relationship with Frankenstein’s sister-in-law. Denying this personal need or preventing such relationships again constitutes a perversion of responsible engagement with creation.

A third thematic field in the film arises from the creature’s existential question about the meaning of its existence and how to deal with its undeserved conditions (original sin). This question becomes all the more existential as the creature increasingly realizes that its being is an experiment and a patchwork of the bodies of various deceased persons – undeniably not a natural product but a forced existence. The creature can never move beyond this experimental, initially arbitrary state, and due to its constantly regenerating physical powers, it can never return to a previous condition. It must therefore live with the inescapable consequences of eternal, albeit material, life in an unwanted shell. This makes the Christian insight all the more important that the meaning of an existence cannot be derived solely from the reasons for its origin, but that existence itself possesses intrinsic value (Grey, 2019).

The creature’s autonomous actions and its ability to choose its own experiences as a self-aware person constitute the true meaning of its existence, far more than the creation motives of its originator. These motives may be one element in the formation of personal identity, but they are not indispensable for personality development. As personality matures, the motives of autonomy and self-efficacy should play an increasingly significant role, for they provide a relevant justification for one’s own existence (Rahner, 1976: 101-103). Viktor Frankl, for example, presents this pragmatic interpretation of existence as the foundation of his logotherapy (Frankl, 1972). The imago-dei character of the Christian creation narrative testifies to the same

⁵ For further reading to Martin Bubers concept of I and Thou, cf. Ravenscroft, 2018.

insight: “image” does not mean external resemblance to the Creator, but rather the capacity to grow into a life shaped by personal responsibility and autonomous creative power – and to use this productively. Discovering one’s own creative power is thus an expression of responsible autonomy (Kelly, 2025; Müller 2020: 25-28).

In this sense, the film fittingly concludes with the creature’s decision to forgive Frankenstein. Forgiveness, as the granting of another’s faults, is the self-determined act of releasing the perpetrator from the relationship of guilt without forgetting or erasing the wrongdoing. Forgiveness despite unatoned guilt is the highest form of autonomy, because it relinquishes the victim’s claim to atonement and withholds from the perpetrator the compensatory performance of such atonement (Brandt, 2024). Thus, insofar as the creature forgives Frankenstein – who is likely incapable of easing the creature’s fate – it proves itself truly autonomous, because it abandons the demand for atonement, for instance through a spiral of violence. Breaking the cycle of violence identifies the originator of violence as guilty but refrains from demanding atonement. In the face of indelible guilt, renouncing violence can be a form of absolute empowerment, as the command to love one’s enemies (Mt 5:43–48; Lk 6:27–36) expresses (Ekman, 2021). In situations of overwhelming power imbalance or escalating violence, restraint becomes a surprising weapon. This does not deny the right to self-defense, but it shows a final path out of entanglement in guilt.

Taken together, the issues addressed reveal *Frankenstein* as a powerful drama about the human being as a mini-creator. The film offers a model-like illustration of how misguided creative power combined with Machiavellian egoism leads to human tragedy. The true redeemer figure is the victim itself, which learns to value its autonomy – stemming from experiences of empowerment and encouragement – as a possibility rather than a curse. Thus, the film inspires hope that human beings, despite their limited view of their own actions, may hope for forgiveness through genuine encounter. Refreshingly open to theological argument, the film also illustrates the relationships between the concepts of creation, creature, and responsibility for creation.

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